

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF CSR ACTIVITIES OF SYNGENTA INDIA ON THE LIVES OF WOMEN FOLKS AT MARCEL VILLAGE, GOA STATE, INDIA

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Abstract

As a sustainable agriculture company, Syngenta India are focused on delivering effective solutions to issues impacting rural communities. Syngenta India CSR interventions work towards balancing economic prosperity, environmental responsibility and social benefits for the community. The study of the impact of CSR activities on the women folk is significant. Whatever be the developmental projects, it reaches its zenith of success only when it touches the lives of the people from all segments of the society. When CSR aims at the betterment of the society, it embraces the women folk too. Women were once considered as the weaker section of the society. But it can no more be said so. They are emerging as one of the most powerful and influential strata of the present society. The broad objective of the study is to understand the socio-economic development of the women folk of Marcel village and to know the level of impact of CSR activities of Syngenta India on the lives of women folk of Marcel village. The Specific objectives of the study is to know the impact of CSR activities (SHG) of Syngenta India on self-esteem of the women folk, social recognition of the women folk and to know the impact of CSR activities (SHG) of Syngenta India on the over-all economic status of the women folk of Marcel village, Goa state, India.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Women Folk, Self-Esteem, Social Recognition, Economic Status.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate social responsibility is a form of corporate self-regulation integrated into a business model. CSR policy functions as a built-in, self-regulating mechanism whereby businesses monitors and ensures its active compliance with the spirit of the law, ethical standards, and international norms.

The goal of CSR is to embrace responsibility for the company's actions and encourage a positive impact through its activities on the environment, consumers, employees, communities, stakeholders and all other members of the public sphere.

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development: "Corporate Social Responsibility is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community and society at large."

Focusing on three key areas for Corporate Social Responsibility can help generate a consistent map for the present and future:

- Community Relations
- Training and Development
- A Cohesive Global Corporate Social Responsibility Platform

Encouraging Community Relations through HR team includes implementing reward programs, charitable contributions and encouraging community involvement and practices. Examples of these programs include sending emails and company newsletters to staff members that highlight employees and managers involved in community relations or creating monthly reward programs to recognize efforts by individuals within the company.

Syngenta AG is a large global Swiss agribusiness company which notably markets seeds and pesticides. Syngenta is involved in biotechnology and genomic research. The company is a leader in crop protection, and ranks third in total sales in the commercial agricultural seeds market. Sales in 2010 were approximately US\$ 11.6 billion. Syngenta employs over 26,000 people in over 90 countries. Syngenta is listed on both the Swiss stock exchange and in New York. Syngenta's Corporate Responsibility Policy established in 2006 formalizes the principles that guide Syngenta in all its business activities. Responsibility for implementing the policy approved by the Board of Directors lies with the Syngenta Executive Committee. In this it is supported by a Corporate Responsibility Committee.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study of the impact of CSR activities on the women folk is significant. Whatever be the developmental projects, it reaches its zenith of success only when it touches the lives of the people from all segments of the society. When CSR aims at the betterment of the society, it embraces the women folk too. Women were once considered as the weaker section of the society. But it can no more be said so. They are emerging as one of the most powerful and influential strata of the present society. It is in this scenario, a study on the impact of CSR activities on the life of women folk of Marcel in Goa is important. This research includes the study of socio-economic background of the women folk and the level of impact of CSR activities of Syngenta India on the personal, social and economic development of the women folk in Marcel.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study is important because nowadays companies have realized the importance of CSR activities.
- ❖ CSR activities help in building a better rapport with the society and creates a goodwill about the company among the people.

- ❖ Women empowerment is possible through CSR activities mainly by establishing self-help groups. Self-help groups can impoverish the financial status of the women folk.
- ❖ It can aid in the social and personal development of the women community too.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Main Objectives

1. To understand the socio-economic development of the women folk of Marcel village.
2. To know the level of impact of CSR activities of Syngenta India on the lives of women folk of Marcel village.

Sub-Objectives

1. To know the impact of CSR activities (SHG) of Syngenta India on self-esteem of the women folk of Marcel village, Goa state, India.
2. To know the impact of CSR activities (SHG) of Syngenta India on the social recognition of the women folk of Marcel village, Goa state, India.
3. To know the impact of CSR activities (SHG) of Syngenta India on the over-all economic status of the women folk of Marcel village, Goa state, India.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Organization here refers to Syngenta India.

The term **respondent's** means the individual members of the various self-help groups of Marcel in Goa which are run as a part of CSR activities of the organization.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research may be classified based on the methods or research design used. Research design is a blue print of a research; it acts as a guideline for the research. According to Henry M research design is a process which not only anticipates and specifies the countless decisions connected with carrying out data collection processing and analysis etc... but it presents a logical base for these decisions also.

The research design of this study was descriptive in nature. Descriptive study is a fact finding investigation with adequate interpretation, it focus on particular aspects and dimensions of the problem studied, it is designed to gather descriptive information and provides information for formulating more sophisticated study. The present study proposed to describe the impact of CSR activities of Syngenta India on the social economical and personal development of the women folk of Marcel in Goa.

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

The universe considered for the present study was the women folk of Marcel in Goa, where the target group was selected for the study. The sample size was taken as 50.

SOURCE OF DATA

The source of data for the research consists of primary data and secondary data which are directly collected from the respondents using a standard questionnaire and the data collected from the organization.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

The researcher collected data from respondents during the month of December 2011 through typed questionnaire. The investigator took two weeks to complete the data collection.

TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

The tool used for this study was questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of four parts:

1. Personal data
2. Personality development
3. Social development
4. Economic development

The questionnaire was an arbitrary one (two point scale).

HYPOTHESIS

A hypothesis is a conjectural statement of the relation between two or more variables. A research hypothesis is a statement, which the study may prove or disprove. Hypothesis helps the researcher in processing further and finding solution to the problem.

H1: There is no significant association between employment status of the respondents and self-esteem.

H2: There is no significant association between employment status of the respondents and social recognition.

H3: There is no significant association between employment status of the respondents and improvement in economic status.

FINDINGS

- Among the respondents 40% belong to the age-group of 39-48 years and all the respondents are females.
- The highest educational qualification held for 50% of the respondents is primary schooling.
- 54% of the respondents are un-employed.
- Majority of the respondents (78%) agreed that SHGs have improved their self-awareness.

- Majority of the respondents (78%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to explore their inner potentials.
- Majority of the respondents (82%) agreed that SHGs have improved their self-esteem.
- Majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that SHGs have improved their level of confidence.
- Majority of the respondents (70%) agreed that SHGs have improved their sense of responsibility.
- Majority of the respondents (86%) agreed that SHGs have improved their will power.
- Majority of the respondents (82%) agreed that SHGs have improved their problem solving skills.
- Majority of the respondents (86%) agreed that SHGs have helped them in managing stress.
- Majority of the respondents (80%) agreed that SHGs have helped them in facing the challenges of life.
- Majority of the respondents (70%) agreed that SHGs have improved their analytical skills.
- Majority of the respondents (86%) agreed that SHGs have helped them in using their time more efficiently.
- Majority of the respondents (84%) agreed that SHGs have made them more ambitious.
- Majority of the respondents (60%) agreed that SHGs have not improved their communicative skills.
- Majority of the respondents (80%) agreed that SHGs have improved their leadership skills.
- Majority of the respondents (96%) agreed that SHGs have improved their social recognition.
- Majority of the respondents (94%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to gain more respect from the society.
- Majority of the respondents (96%) agreed that SHGs have made them more socially responsible.
- Half of the respondents (50%) agreed that SHGs have improved their social awareness.
- Majority of the respondents (66%) agreed that SHGs have improved their commitment towards the society.

- Majority of the respondents (76%) agreed that SHGs have made them more contributory towards the society.
- Majority of the respondents (64%) agreed that SHGs have not made political conscious.
- Majority of the respondents (76%) agreed that SHGs have improved their participation in community development programmes.
- Majority of the respondents (92%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to shoulder their family responsibilities.
- Majority of the respondents (86%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to improve the health status of their family members.
- Majority of the respondents (80%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to provide better education for their children.
- Majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that SHGs have brought joy and happiness to their life.
- Majority of the respondents (92%) agreed that SHGs have reduced their financial liabilities and debts.
- Majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that SHGs have improved their habit of savings.
- Majority of the respondents (52%) agreed that SHGs have increased their economic assets.
- Majority of the respondents (80%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to renovate their house.
- Majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that SHGs have helped them to escape from the clutches of poverty.
- Majority of the respondents (78%) agreed that SHGs have improved their level of income.
- Majority of the respondents (70%) agreed that SHGs have improved their economic status.
- Majority of the respondents (84%) agreed that SHGs have improved their comfort of materialistic life.

SUGGESTIONS

- The economic benefits of the members of self-help groups can be increased if they engage in any productive (economic) activity.
- Members can be encouraged to start up an economic activity by giving rewards and social recognition to the women entrepreneurs.

- Success stories of such women entrepreneurs should be shared with other fellow members of the group.
- More economic advantages and privileges should be given to the members who initiate an economic activity.
- Women should be made aware about economic independence.

CONCLUSION

The study on the impact of CSR activities of Syngenta India on the women folk of Marcel, Goa gave the researcher a complete positive response. The study revealed that it has immense positive effect on the personal, social and economic growth and development of the women folk of Marcel. In short, it can be said that it has touched many a lives of Marcel in a big way, creating better and beautiful lives. To put it in other words, the life has been made easier and smoother for the women folk of Marcel. But the only slight drawback which the researcher found during the course of study was that proper importance is not given by the members of self-help groups to undertake an economic (productive) activity. The work undertaken by them is appreciable, where they are into pappad making, flower making etc... Even though, income generating activities are carried out by some of the groups, it fails to meet the mark sometimes. A shift of such an attitude, can further add to the economic growth of the members. It is possible by a strong and continuous support from the family, Syngenta India Ltd and from the NGO Margadarshak.

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